

ISSN 2320 - 9461

COMMERCE TIMES

International research journal of commerce

Volume 1

Issue 2

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A STUDY ON WORK VALUES AND ROLE STRESS AMONG THE ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY TEACHERS

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Teachers are the key agents through which educational plans are achieved. Their responsibility is as heavy as the entire educational goals and societies' ideals and aspirations. The teacher's role is so significant that many studies have been conducted exploring his behavior and motivation in his work (*Domingo, 1989*)

It becomes an inspiration, therefore, to maintain a system of motivation to ensure the teachers commitment to carry out with zealous devotion their responsibility of educating the youth. They are directly responsible for quality education, dissemination of knowledge and development of sound attitudes and values of school clientele.

The recent issues about teachers strike protest and post turnovers are strong indicators that dissatisfaction had invaded the world of pedagogy - evidence that the teachers are human. They too, have to respond to the demand of their personal welfare which is at present undoubtedly jeopardized. It would be well to remember that the most people work predominantly, not in the pursuit of personal glory, but in order to live at least with some degree of responsibility and dignity. People have joined the teaching force because they believed that aside from contributing to the realization of fundamental aims of education, they also have to satisfy their personal needs.

Teaching can be both rewarding and frustrating. Rewarding in the sense that the teachers have the greatest opportunity of touching the lives of the people; of engaging in a variety of activities, and of contributing to the well being of society. Frustrating- because on the top of the heavy work load in institution, teachers are also expected to perform other duties which take most of their time which should be devoted for lesson planning and for the improvement of their

instructional materials. Moreover, society expects teachers to live a life that is dignified and beyond reproach. But , in return society has done very little to promote the well being of teachers.

Researchers suggest that the quality of work of teachers in school is a product of the interaction of several factors such as values, attitudes, beliefs, and satisfaction of workers (*Rossmiller 1992*).

In all organizations, the employees are characterized by their work values. Their work values are the perception toward their work in general that is - the employees themselves, management practices, outside facets and even state of communication. It is concerned as an influential factor in job performance. It is the goal, vision which motivates man to action. The level of success of certain productivity and motivation technique, therefore, depends upon the work values of the individual.

Faculty members should be made to feel more satisfied in order to give more to their teaching function. They need involvement in their own professional development and this must be supplemented by a promotion policy and at the same time schools must create new opportunities. Teaching connotes that the instructions can influence the values of their students, since values realization is an educative process involving people.

Theoretical Framework

There are varied reasons why people work. They may work because they love to and they find fulfillment in doing it, or they may work because they are compelled to do it. Whatever their reasons for working are, these, to some extent, have to do with satisfying their needs (*Andres 1980*).

However, the reasons people do a particular kind of work may not necessarily be the same reasons for continuing to stay in the same area and in the same kind of work. Although, it is often and popularly believed that people who

stay in an organization for a long time, doing the same kind of work are, to some extent satisfied.

In an effort to fully understand what causes work values and job satisfaction, a thorough study was made by the researcher based on the many theories about needs, work values, performance organizational rewards, motivation, and job satisfaction. Each aspect is carefully studied in the light of their relationship to work values and job satisfaction. The legislature assumes that there is talk of work stress if the employee attributes their stress symptoms to their work. This approach is in line with the perception of the stress process in the individual as described by Bakker, De Jonge and Taris (2003). Bakker et al describe that an objective stressor should firstly be experienced before this can have a psychological effect on the person.

Employees are not always aware of the objective stressors that are present. Objective stressors that are not experienced also do not lead to stress (Bakker et al, 2003). Gaillard (1992) described that stress only arises when a person thinks that the disharmony between the demands, which are set by the immediate surroundings, and the ability of the person to do the job. Buunk and De Wolff (1992) indicate that in cases of stress it primarily concerns all those situations that give cause for negative feelings in people. De Jonge, Le Blanc and Schaufeli (2003) describe work stress as stress during or through the work situation. An individual's perception of stress is a symptom which can be attributed to a stressor in the work situation. From the definitions as described and the perception of the person, work stress can be psychologically understood to comprise two aspects: symptoms of stress and stressors.

Work stress is defined by attributing symptoms of stress to stressors. This definition is based on the premise that both are inextricably connected with each other (holistic approach). Work stress comprises symptoms of stress that are attributed to stressors (see Figure 1).

Fig1: Model of work stress

Therefore the components of work stress are inseparable in a psychological sense; just as the beach is made up of the sea and the sand. Remove one of the aspects, then this is no longer a beach; there is no work stress.

People experience symptoms of stress and, in case of work stress, attribute those same symptoms of stress to stressors. People couple the inner perception of symptoms of stress to the perception of stressors in their surroundings. In other words, people give a meaning to their symptoms of stress by pointing the symptoms to sources in the work situation (stressors). Work stress is a form of identification, of giving a meaning.

Work stress

As a general rule, actions to reduce job stress should give top priority to organizational change to improve working conditions. But even the most conscientious efforts to improve working conditions are unlikely to eliminate stress completely for all workers. For this reason, a combination of organizational change and stress management is often the most useful approach for preventing stress at work.

Change the organization to prevent Work stress

- ❖ Ensure that the workload is in line with workers' capabilities and resources.
- ❖ Design jobs to provide meaning, stimulation, and opportunities for workers to use their skills.

- ❖ Clearly define workers' roles and responsibilities.
- ❖ Give workers opportunities to participate in decisions and actions affecting their jobs.
- ❖ Improve communications-reduce uncertainty about career development and future employment prospects.
- ❖ Provide opportunities for social interaction among workers.
- ❖ Establish work schedules that are compatible with demands and responsibilities outside the job.

WORK VALUES	JOB STRESS
creativity	Demands
achievement	Control
management	Support
surroundings	Relationships
supervisory relations	Role
way of life	Change
security	
association	
aesthetic	
independence	
varsity	
economic return	
altruism	
prestige	

Review Of Literature

Work is described as the noblest expression of man's self and is considered the bigger source of fulfillment (Villegas, 1983). It provides one with a sense of identity. It tells others who and what one is. It contributes to a person's sense of self-esteem, affiliation and belonging (Schultz, 1982). The church encyclical on work states that through work, "man fulfills himself as a man and is also in a sense, even more becomes a man" (Pope John Paul II, 1982).

For man to work is a birthright. It is a constitutional right, which is protected by various provisions of the constitution. But it is also a responsibility. Every man is duty bound to find a proper job and do it properly (Magturo, 1985). Thus, in the words of Pope John II: “Work is a duty or obligation of a man in the multiple sense of this word. Man should work both on account of the instructions of the creator or on account of his own humanity, whose preservation and development require work. Man should work not only for the sake of dear ones, especially for his family, but also for the society to which he belongs, for the nation for whose son or daughter he or she is, for the entire human family of which he is a member, being an heir of the work of generations and at the same time a co-creator of the future of those who will come after him in history. All of these makers up the broadly understood moral obligations of work>”

It flows from this teaching that man works because of various reasons. He may work for economic security or social mobility; or man works because of his concern for his family, relatives and friends; or he may work for his community, society and nation and on the spiritual dimension, man may work to participate in a greater work of creation (Meralco, 1983).

Methodology

Hypotheses

This study attempted to test the following hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers' work values.
2. There are no significant differences among the different areas of work stress.
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' work values and role stress

Sources Of Data

Primary data is collected from teaching faculty of Annamalai University by using a standard format Questionnaire.

Universe

Researcher planned to study the work values and work stress of all faculties (75)

Annalmalai University who is attending refresher course on June 2012. So that the universe is definite population

Sampling

The researcher collected data from 50 officers (out of 75) by using purposive / convenience sampling method.

Tools Of Analysis

The researcher has used various tools of analysis. The descriptive statistics such as Mean, and Standard deviation test and chi square test were computed.

Analysis And Interpretation

Age & Opinion about Work Values

		age			
		25-34	35-44	45-54	more than 55
Work values	unimportant	0	0	0	0
	little important	0	1	0	0
	moderately important	0	2	0	0
	important	4	13	1	0
	very important	7	18	4	0

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		age
Work values	Chi-square	2.442
	df	6
	Sig.	.875

The above tables infer that there is no significance with respondents age and with there opinion about the importance of values in their work, so from this table it we can able to understand respondents age is not a factor for producing stress for teachers.

Sex & Opinion about Work Values

		SEX	
		male	female
Work values	unimportant	0	0
	little important	1	0
	moderately important	1	1
	important	7	11
	very important	13	16

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		SEX
Work values	Chi-square	1.501
	df	3
	Sig.	.682

The above tables infer that there is no significance with respondents sex and with there opinion about the importance of values in there work

Designation & Getting Irritated

		Get More irritated				
		poor student behave	management policies	work with personal	misunderstanding	none
desig resp	Asst prof	15	13	7	5	9
	Asso prof	1	0	0	0	0
	prof	0	0	0	0	0

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		More irritated *
desig resp	Chi-square	2.168
	df	4
	Sig.	.705

The above tables shows that there is no significant relation ship with the respondents designation and there feelings on irritated to some situation. so there is no significant relation ship with the two things.

Sex & responsibility sharing

		sex	
		male	female
sharing resp	family	6	17
	friends	6	6
	colleagues	4	2
	none	6	3

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		sex
sharing resp	Chi-square	6.298
	df	3
	Sig.	.098 ^a

The above tables shows that there is no significant relation ship with the respondents sex and there shares about there stressful situation related to there work life ,so there is no significant relation ship with the two things.

Work values, Health problems & Leaves

		health problem							no ne	
		head ache	B P	obesit y	diabete s	heart disease	respiratory problem	digestive problem		
Work value s	unimportant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	little	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	
	important									
	moderately	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	important	8	1	4	2	0	1	0	2	
	very	10	0	1	4	0	2	2	10	
	important									
	leave s	less than 2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
	2-5	7	1	2	0	0	0	0	4	
	5-10	9	1	2	4	0	3	0	5	
more than 10	3	0	2	0	0	0	2	3		

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		health problem
Work values	Chi-square	28.080
	df	18
	Sig.	.061
leaves	Chi-square	31.715
	df	18
	Sig.	.024

The above tables shows the relationship between health problems of the respondents with their leaves on one year and with their opinion about the importance of work values it on the way infer that there is no significant between the health problems and importance about the work values, but there is significance between the health problems with there leaves they taken in one year.

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		health problem
Work values	Chi-square	28.080
	df	18
	Sig.	.061
leaves	Chi-square	31.715
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Work Values & Work Stress

		Work Values				
		unimportant	little important	moderately important	important	very important
Work Stress	not at all	0	0	0	0	2
	not much	0	0	1	7	1
	sometimes	0	0	0	4	11
	mostly	0	0	1	7	5
	very much so	0	1	0	0	10

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

		Work values
Work Stress	Chi-square	24.340
	df	12
	Sig.	.018 ^{*,a,b}

The above tables clearly show the relationship between the work values and work stress among the respondents the two things are really has the significance between two at 5% level.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- ❖ The faculties who attending Refresher course in Annamalai University, possessed high work values.
- ❖ Female faculties had a higher level of work values than the male teachers.
- ❖ The faculty's health problems significantly related with stress and their leave patterns
- ❖ The faculty respondents revealed that the work values are significantly related to work Stress.

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